

Cordypyridones E–J: Antibiofilm 2-Pyridone Alkaloids from the Nematode Antagonistic Fungus *Laburnicola nematophila*

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ABSTRACT: In the course of biochemical prospection of *Laburnicola nematophila* isolated from eggs of the plant-parasitic cyst nematode *Heterodera filipjevi*, eight 2-pyridone alkaloids were isolated from its solid-state BRFT cultures and identified as six previously undescribed, cordypyridones E–J (1–6), and two known congeners, cordypyridones C (7) and D (8). The structures and absolute configurations of all isolated compounds were elucidated through HR-ESI-MS, 1D/2D NMR spectroscopy, and TDDFT-ECD calculations. Compound 4, bearing a rare *N*-hydroxy-2-pyridone moiety structurally related to that of PF1140, exhibited broad-spectrum bioactivity in cytotoxicity and antimicrobial assays. Compounds 5 and 6 demonstrated potent antibiofilm activities against *Staphylococcus aureus*, reducing its biofilm formation by almost 50% at 0.25 and 7.8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively.

Fungi are an established source of structurally diverse and biologically active natural products, many of which have found applications as pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, or research tools.¹ Despite decades of intensive research, fungal secondary metabolism continues to yield novel scaffolds and bioactivities.² Continuous exploration of underexplored fungal niches remains a key strategy for the discovery of novel secondary metabolites.^{1,3} Among these, cyst nematodes provide a promising source for isolating their associated fungi many of which produced a diverse array of bioactive compounds.^{4–8} These fungi live in close association with nematodes, which are among the most abundant and ecologically significant invertebrates.⁹ The interaction between fungi and nematodes has likely driven the evolution of specialized metabolites with roles in chemical defense, parasitism, or interspecies communication.⁴

Concurrently, exploring new biofilm inhibitors has become a priority in antimicrobial research.¹⁰ Biofilms, structured microbial communities encased in an extracellular matrix, confer enhanced tolerance to antibiotics/host defenses and are a major factor in chronic infections and medical-device-associated complications.^{9,11,12} The development of compounds that can inhibit biofilm formation or disrupt mature biofilms, ideally without promoting resistance or causing cytotoxicity, is urgently needed. Natural products offer an attractive starting point for such agents, given their structural diversity and evolutionary optimization for biological activity.

In this context, we investigated the secondary metabolome of *Laburnicola nematophila*, a fungus derived from infected

cysts of the plant-parasitic nematode *Heterodera filipjevi*,¹³ which was reported as the producer of diverse classes of bioactive metabolites including the potent antifungal poly-alcohol α -pyrone dactylfungins, tetralones and peptides.^{5–7} In this study, the chemical investigation led to the identification of six previously undescribed pyridone alkaloids (1–6) and the known compounds cordypyridones C (7) and D (8).¹⁴ Their structures were determined by a combination of HR-ESI-MS, NMR spectroscopy, and TDDFT-ECD calculations. The antimicrobial, cytotoxic, nematocidal, and biofilm inhibitory properties of the isolated compounds were assessed. This study describes the chromatographic separation, comprehensive structure elucidation, and biological evaluation of the isolated natural products.

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Table 1. ¹H and ¹³C NMR Data of 1–4

position	1		2		3		4	
	δ_C^a type	δ_H^a multi [J(Hz)]	δ_C^a type	δ_H^a multi [J(Hz)]	δ_C^b type	δ_H^b multi [J(Hz)]	δ_C^a type	δ_H^a multi [J(Hz)]
2	159.7, CO		160.0, CO		164.6, CO		159.3, CO	
3	110.8, C		110.8, C		109.3, C		109.5, C	
4	165.7, C		165.7, C		167.7, C		164.5, C	
5	100.6, CH	5.89 d (7.7)	100.9, CH	5.91 d (7.7)	101.7, CH	5.90 d (7.0)	99.1, CH	5.89 d (7.5)
6	134.6, CH	7.63 dd (7.7, 0.8)	134.9, CH	7.65 dd (7.7, 0.8)	133.6, CH	7.14 dd (7.0)	133.1, CH	7.62 d (7.5)
7	50.8, CH	2.05 d (11.5)	51.2, CH	2.07 d (11.4)	50.2, CH	2.02 d (11.5)	50.4, CH	2.03 d (11.3)
8	37.0, C		37.2, C		36.9, C		37.3, C	
9	47.8, CH ₂	α 1.09 d (13.2) β 1.74 dd (13.2, 2.8)	41.1, CH ₂	α 0.71 m (overlapped) β 1.76 dt (12.0, 2.5)	47.7, CH ₂	α 1.09 d (13.7) β 1.74 dd (13.7, 2.8)	46.5, CH ₂	α 0.70 t (13.1) β 1.62 m (overlapped)
10	69.7, C		35.3, CH	1.70 dqd (12.4, 6.1, 3.1)	69.6, C		27.0, CH	1.64 m (overlapped)
11	49.0, CH ₂	α 1.04 dd (14.0, 1.9) β 1.85 ddd (14.0, 4.3, 2.8)	40.3, CH ₂	α 0.65 m (overlapped) β 1.91 ddt (13.2, 4.8, 2.9)	49.0, CH ₂	α 1.04 dd (14.1, 12.2) β 1.84 ddd (14.0, 4.3, 2.8)	46.1, CH ₂	α 0.63 dd (13.1) β 1.84 ddt (13.1, 4.9, 2.9)
12	25.2, CH	2.84 dqd (12.0, 6.0, 4.3)	28.9, CH	2.61 dqd (12.0, 5.9, 4.8)	25.0, CH	2.79 dqd (11.9, 5.9, 4.3)	28.9, CH	2.56 tq (11.3, 5.7)
13	88.3, CH	4.10 q (6.5)	87.7, CH	4.16 q (6.5)	88.0, CH	4.09 q (6.5)	87.3, CH	4.13 q (6.5)
14	15.8, CH ₃	1.19 d (6.5)	16.0, CH ₃	1.23 d (6.5)	15.8, CH ₃	1.19 d (6.5)	15.7, CH ₃	1.21 d (6.5)
15	16.4, CH ₃	0.82 s	14.9, CH ₃	0.69 s	16.2, CH ₃	0.83 s	14.7, CH ₃	0.66 s
16	32.7, CH ₃	1.21 s	68.6, CH ₂	α 3.34 dd (10.6, 4.1) β 3.40 dd (10.6, 6.0)	32.7, CH ₃	1.20 s	22.9, CH ₃	0.91 d (6.4)
17	24.9, CH ₃	1.15 d (6.0)	25.6, CH ₃	1.16 d (5.8)	24.7, CH ₃	1.14 d (5.9)	25.3, CH ₃	1.15 d (5.7)
18	65.0, CH ₃	3.93 s	65.2, CH ₃	3.93 s				

^aMeasured in methanol-*d*₄ at 500 MHz for ¹H and 125 MHz for ¹³C. ^bMeasured in methanol-*d*₄ at 700 MHz for ¹H and 175 MHz for ¹³C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation and Identification of Compounds 1–8.

Compound **1** was obtained as a yellow amorphous solid. Its molecular formula was established as C₁₇H₂₅NO₄ based on HR-ESI-MS (Figure S1), which showed a protonated molecular ion peak at m/z 308.1857 [M + H]⁺ (calculated 308.1856), indicating six degrees of unsaturation. The ¹³C NMR and HSQC spectral data of **1** (Table 1 and Figures S4 and S7) revealed 17 carbon signals, categorized into five unprotonated, including a carbonyl carbon, and five methines accounting for three degrees of unsaturation together with two methylenes and five methyls including a methoxy group. Based on the ¹³C NMR spectral data analysis, compound **1** was deduced to comprise a tricyclic structure. The ¹H NMR and ¹H–¹H COSY spectra of **1** (Table 1, Figure 1, and Figures S3

Figure 1. Key ¹H–¹H COSY and HMBC correlations of 1–6.

and S5) revealed the presence of three spin systems corresponding to those revealed by the known compound cordypyridone C (7).¹² A literature search of **1** revealed its structural resemblance to cordypyridones A–D, *N*-hydroxy- and *N*-methoxy-2-pyridone alkaloids previously reported from the entomopathogenic fungus *Pleurocordyceps nipponica*.¹⁴ The structure of **1** appeared to be different from cordypyridone C (7) only in the presence of a tertiary alcohol moiety at C-10. Its HMBC spectrum was acquired and the obtained results (Figure 1 and Figure S6) revealed key correlations that confirmed the depicted structure of **1**. The relative configuration of **1** was determined via its ROESY spectrum (Figure 2 and Figure S8) that revealed key ROE correlations between H₃-17/H-7/H-13/H α -9/H α -11 indicating their projection toward the same face of the molecule whereas key ROE

correlations were noted between H-12/H₃-15/H₃-14/H β -9/H β -11 indicating that they are facing the opposite side of the molecule. The absolute configuration of **1** was determined based on the similarity between its measured and calculated TDDFT–ECD spectra (Figure 3). As can be seen from Figure 3, a close coherence was observed between the experimental ECD spectrum and that predicted for the (7*R*,8*R*,10*S*,12*S*,13*S*) configuration over the whole range. Based on the obtained results, compound **1** was identified as a previously undescribed *N*-methoxy-2-pyridone alkaloid named cordypyridone E.

Compound **2** was purified as a yellow amorphous solid whose HR-ESI-MS spectrum (Figure S10) determined its molecular formula as C₁₇H₂₅NO₄ by revealing a protonated molecular ion peak at m/z 308.1855 [M + H]⁺ (calculated 308.1856) indicating six degrees of unsaturation similar to **1**. The ¹³C and ¹H NMR spectral data of **2** (Table 1) revealed an obvious resemblance to **1** despite having clearly different retention times in their HPLC chromatograms (Figures S1 and S2 for **1** and Figures S9 and S10 for **2**). A comparison of the ¹H/¹³C NMR spectral data of **1** and **2** (Table 1) revealed the replacement of a nonprotonated sp³ carbon at δ_C 69.7 (C-10) and a singlet methyl group at δ_H 1.21 (H₃-16; δ_C 32.7) in **1** by an aliphatic methine at δ_H 1.70 (dq, J = 12.4, 6.1, 3.1 Hz, H-10; δ_C 35.3) coupled to a diastereotopic oxymethylene group at δ_H 3.34/3.40 (H₂-16; δ_C 68.6). Apart from these differences, the ¹H/¹³C NMR spectral data of **1** and **2** (Table 1) are quite comparable. To confirm the depicted structure of **2**, its ¹H–¹H COSY and HMBC data (Figure 1 and Figures S13 and S14) were acquired confirming the connection of CH₂–16 and CH-10. The relative configuration of **2** was deduced through its ROESY spectrum (Figure 2 and Figure S16) that revealed key ROE correlations from H-12 to H-10 and H₃-15, suggesting their projection toward the same face of the molecule while H-7 was correlated to H-13 and H₃-17 indicating that they are facing the opposite side of the molecule. Regarding the absolute configuration of **2**, a good fit was observed between the experimental ECD and the calculated TDDFT–ECD for the (7*R*,8*R*,10*R*,12*S*,13*S*) configuration (Figure 4). Accordingly, compound **2** was deduced to be a previously undescribed *N*-methoxy-2-pyridone alkaloid that was given the trivial name cordypyridone F.

Compound **3** was isolated as a yellow amorphous solid with its HR-ESI-MS spectrum (Figure S18), determining its molecular formula as C₁₆H₂₃NO₃ by revealing a protonated molecular ion peak at m/z 278.1748 [M + H]⁺ (calculated 278.1751) and thus indicating six degrees of unsaturation equal to those in **1** and **2**. By comparing the molecular formulas of **1**–**3**, the latter was found to lack the CH₂O moiety, accounting for its smaller molecular weight. By comparing the ¹³C, ¹H, and 2D NMR spectral data of **1**–**3** (Table 1, Figures 1 and 2, and Figures S20–S23), it was clearly observed that compound **3** is closely similar to **1**, lacking one methoxy group bound to the nitrogen in **1**. The absolute configuration of **3** was confirmed by comparing its experimental and calculated ECD spectra (Figure 5), revealing a similar pattern with the conformer featuring the (7*R*,8*R*,10*S*,12*S*,13*S*) configuration. Therefore, compound **3** was identified as shown and trivially named cordypyridone G.

Compound **4** was obtained as a yellow amorphous solid with its molecular formula established as C₁₆H₂₃NO₃ by revealing a protonated molecular ion peak at m/z 278.1751 [M + H]⁺ (calculated 278.1751) and thus indicating six degrees of unsaturation as **3**. By comparing the ¹³C and ¹H NMR spectral

Figure 2. Key ROESY correlations of 1–6.

Figure 3. Measured and calculated ECD spectra of 1 in MeOH.

Figure 5. Measured and calculated ECD spectra of 3 in MeOH.

Figure 4. Measured and calculated ECD spectra of 2 in MeOH.

data of 2 and 4 (Table 1), it was clear that the oxymethylene moiety in 2 is replaced by a doublet methyl group in 4. In addition, a second difference between 2 and 4 was noticed, namely the absence of the methoxy group. Based on the obtained results and a literature search of 4, it was suggested to be a demethylated derivative of cordypyridone C (7), first reported from the insect pathogenic fungus *P. nipponica*,¹⁴ fusaricide, a reported cytotoxic metabolite from *Fusarium* sp.,¹⁵ and asperpyridone A from an endophytic *Aspergillus* sp.¹⁶ The structure of 4 was ascertained through comprehensive 2D NMR spectral analyses (Figures 1 and 2 and Figures S27–S30) and comparison with the reported literature,¹⁶ which revealed it as an analogue of 7 with a hydroxyl replacing the methoxy group at the nitrogen. The relative configuration of 4 was identified through its ROESY spectrum (Figure 2 and Figure S30) that revealed comparable key ROE correlations to those of compounds 1–3 (Figure 2). The absolute configuration of 4 was determined based on the comparison between its experimental and calculated TDDFT–ECD spectra (Figure 6), and the obtained results revealed a close coherence of the measured ECD spectrum to that calculated for the conformer adopting the (7R,8R,10R,12S,13S) configuration. According to

Figure 6. Measured and calculated ECD spectra of 4 in MeOH.

the obtained results, compound 4 was identified as depicted and named cordypyridone H.

Compound 5 was obtained as a yellow amorphous solid. The HR-ESI-MS spectrum (Figure S32) revealed its protonated molecular ion peak at m/z 354.2061 $[M + H]^+$ (calculated 354.2064) and thus established its molecular formula as $C_{22}H_{27}NO_3$ indicating ten degrees of unsaturation. The 1H NMR and HSQC spectral data of 5 (Table 2 and Figures S33 and S36) unraveled the presence of a deshielded singlet aromatic proton at δ_H 7.13 (H-6) directly correlated to

a carbon atom at δ_C 132.0 in addition to two doublet proton signals each integrated for two hydrogen atoms at δ_H 7.20 and 6.78 with a coupling constant (J value) of 8.6 Hz. The obtained results denoted the presence of a 1,4-disubstituted aromatic ring in 5 compared to compounds 1–4 and suggested its position at C-5 whose corresponding proton signal disappeared in 5. To ascertain the suggested structure modification in 5 compared to 1–4, 2D NMR spectral analyses were acquired, including 1H – 1H COSY, HMBC and ROESY spectra (Figures 1 and 2 and Figures S34, S35, and S37). In addition to the featured spin systems in 1–4, the 1H – 1H COSY data of 5 (Figure 1 and Figure S34) revealed a spin system between H_2 -2',6' and H_2 -3',5'. Further confirmation to the depicted structure of 5 was obtained through its HMBC spectrum (Figure 1 and S35) that revealed key correlations from H_2 -2',6' at δ_H 7.20 (d, J = 8.6 Hz) to a carbon resonance at δ_C 116.4 (C-5) confirming the presence of 4'-hydroxyphenyl moiety at C-5 of the 2-pyridone nucleus. The relative configuration of the 2-pyridone nucleus in 5 was determined based on its ROESY spectrum (Figure 2 and Figure S37), which revealed similar key ROE correlations to those in 4. The absolute configuration of 5 was established based on the comparison of its experimental and calculated TDDFT-ECD spectra. The obtained results revealed a cohering pattern of the measured ECD spectrum to that calculated for the conformer with the configuration of (7R,8R,10R,12S,13S) (Figure 7). A literature search of 5 revealed that it is closely related to several 2-pyridone fungal metabolites despite adopting different stereochemistry including epipyridone A,¹⁷ trichodin A¹⁸ and chaunolidone A.¹⁹ It is noteworthy to mention that a literature search of 5 revealed

Table 2. 1H and ^{13}C NMR Data of 5 and 6

position	5		6	
	δ_C^a type	δ_H^a multi [J (Hz)]	δ_C^b type	δ_H^b multi [J (Hz)]
2	163.9, CO		163.9, CO	
3	109.5, C		109.7, C	
4	165.3, C		165.5, C	
5	116.4, C		116.8, C	
6	132.0, CH	7.13 s	132.0, CH	7.11 d (0.8)
7	50.0, CH	2.02 d (11.3)	50.1, CH	2.02 d (11.4)
8	37.6, C		37.7, C	
9	46.9, CH ₂	α 0.72 m (overlapped) β 1.63 dt (12.6, 2.7)	47.0, CH ₂	α 0.72 m (overlapped) β 1.64 m
10	27.1, CH	1.65 m (overlapped)	27.2, CH	1.64 m (overlapped)
11	46.2, CH ₂	α 0.64 q (12.6) β 1.84 ddt (13.2, 4.8, 2.5)	46.2, CH ₂	α 0.64 q (12.3) β 1.84 m
12	28.9, CH	2.65 tq (11.2, 5.5)	29.0, CH	2.66 m
13	87.9, CH	4.19 q (6.5)	88.0, CH	4.19 q (6.5)
14	15.7, CH ₃	1.16 d (6.5)	15.9, CH ₃	1.18 d (6.5)
15	15.0, CH ₃	0.72 s	15.1, CH ₃	0.72 s
16	22.9, CH ₃	0.91 d (6.2)	23.0, CH ₃	0.91 d (6.3)
17	25.1, CH ₃	1.14 d (5.8)	25.2, CH ₃	1.14 d (5.9)
18				
1'	126.5, C		127.1, C	
2'	131.0, CH	7.20 d (8.6)	117.4, CH	6.84 d (2.1)
3'	115.6, CH	6.78 d (8.6)	145.5, C	
4'	157.6, C		145.8, C	
5'	115.6, CH	6.78 d (8.6)	115.8, CH	6.75 d (8.2)
6'	131.0, CH	7.20 d (8.6)	121.6, CH	6.69 dd (8.2, 2.1)

^aMeasured in methanol- d_4 at 700 MHz for 1H and 175 MHz for ^{13}C . ^bMeasured in methanol- d_4 at 500 MHz for 1H and 125 MHz for ^{13}C .

Figure 7. Measured and calculated ECD spectra of **5** in MeOH.

that it was reported earlier this year in a Chinese patent as a fermentation product from axenic or co-cultures of a marine-derived *Aspergillus aculeatinus* strain for treating acute liver injury.²⁰ Based on the obtained results, compound **5** is reported here for the first time from the nematode-cyst-derived fungus *L. nematophila* and was trivially named cordypyridone I.

Compound **6** was isolated as a yellow amorphous solid. The HR-ESI-MS spectrum of **6** (Figure S39) revealed a protonated molecular ion peak at m/z 370.2013 $[M + H]^+$ (calculated 370.2013) that determined its molecular formula as $C_{22}H_{27}NO_4$ indicating ten degrees of unsaturation equal to those in **5** despite having an additional oxygen atom. The $^1H/^{13}C$ NMR spectral data of **6** (Table 2) were close to identical in comparison with their respective values in **5**.

The only difference that could be noticed is the replacement of the two doublet aromatic proton resonances in **5** by three aromatic proton signals at δ_H 6.84 (d, $J = 2.1$ Hz, H-2'), 6.75 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, H-5') and 6.69 (dd, $J = 8.2, 2.1$ Hz, H-6') that were directly correlated via the HSQC spectrum (Figure S43) to three methine sp^2 carbon atoms at δ_C 117.4 (C-2'), 115.8 (C-5') and 121.6 (C-6'), respectively. The obtained results suggested that the additional oxygen atom in **6** afforded a 1,3,4-trisubstituted aromatic ring. Further confirmation was obtained via the HMBC spectrum (Figure S42) that revealed key correlations from H-2' and H-6' to C-5, C-3' and C-4' indicating that the 3,4-dihydroxyphenyl moiety is bound to C-5 of the 2-pyridone core nucleus. The ROESY spectrum of **6** (Figure S44) revealed similar key ROE correlations to those observed for **5** indicating that they both have a similar spatial orientation of substituents. The absolute configuration of **6** was established based on comparing its experimental and the calculated TDDFT-ECD spectra that revealed similar Cotton effect patterns for the experimental ECD spectrum of **6** and that calculated for the conformer with the configuration of (7R,8R,10R,12S,13S) (Figure 8). Accordingly, compound **6** was recognized as shown and it was named cordypyridone J.

Compounds **7** and **8** were isolated as yellow amorphous solids. Their HR-ESI-MS spectra (Figures S46 and S55) revealed their molecular formulas to be $C_{17}H_{25}NO_3$ and $C_{17}H_{25}NO_4$, respectively. Their structures were elucidated based on comprehensive 1D/2D spectroscopic analyses in addition to comparison with the reported literature.¹⁴

Figure 8. Measured and calculated ECD spectra of **6** in MeOH.

Accordingly, compounds **7** and **8** were identified as cordypyridones C and D, respectively, which were previously reported from the entomopathogenic fungus *Pleurocordyceps nipponica*.¹⁴

Biological Assays. Among the tested compounds, cordypyridone H (**4**), a *N*-hydroxy-2-pyridone structurally related to PF1140,²¹ exhibited the most potent pancytotoxic activity (Table 3) across all tested cell lines (IC₅₀: 0.08–0.35 μ M) and broad antimicrobial activity, with low MIC values against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Escherichia coli*) and several fungi (*Candida albicans*, *Rhodotorula glutinis*, and *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*). No nematicidal effects (see Table S15) were observed for any of the tested compounds. This profile is consistent with reported activities of *N*-hydroxy-2-pyridones, known to interfere with microbial and eukaryotic targets.²² In contrast, compounds **1**, **2**, **5**, **6**, and **7** exhibited limited cytotoxic activity. Only compound **5** showed moderate antibacterial effects (Table 3), while compound **7** displayed weak cytotoxicity against KB3.1 cells.

In the antibiofilm assay, compounds **1**–**3** and **5**–**8** exhibited varying levels of inhibitory activity against the formation of *S. aureus* biofilms (Figure 9 and Table S1), with **5** being the most effective. Compounds **5**–**7** inhibited the biofilm formation by more than 75% at a concentration of 125 μ g/mL. In particular, cordypyridone I (**5**) revealed biofilm inhibitory activity by ca. 43% even at a low concentration of 0.25 μ g/mL, indicating a strong dose-dependent effect. Additionally, cordypyridones J (**6**) and C (**7**) displayed significant biofilm inhibition by 54 and 51% at 7.8 and 15.6 μ g/mL, respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

General Experimental Procedures. A Shimadzu UV-vis spectrophotometer UV-2450 (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) was used to record the UV-vis spectra. An Anton Paar MCP-150 polarimeter (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) was used for measuring optical rotation values at 20 °C. A Jasco J-815 spectropolarimeter (Jasco, Pfungstadt, Germany) was used to acquire the ECD spectra. An amaZon speed ETD ion trap mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) was used to conduct the HPLC-DAD-MS analysis in positive and negative ionization modes. As a stationary phase, a C₁₈ Acquity UPLC BEH column (50 \times 2.1 mm, 1.7 μ m Waters, MA, U.S.A.) connected to the HPLC system (Dionex UltiMate 3000

Table 3. Cytotoxicity (μM) and Antimicrobial Activity Assay (MIC) of 1, 2, and 4–7^a

test cell line	IC ₅₀ (μM)						positive control
	1	2	4	5	6	7	epothilone B (nM)
mouse fibroblast (L929)	*	*	0.28	**	**	**	0.65
human endocervical adenocarcinoma (KB3.1)	*	*	0.35	**	**	61.86	0.17
human prostate carcinoma (PC-3)	n.d.	n.d.	9.37	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.09
human breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7)	n.d.	n.d.	0.10	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.07
human ovarian cancer (SKOV-3)	n.d.	n.d.	0.08	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.09
human epidermoid carcinoma (A431)	n.d.	n.d.	0.08	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.06
human lung carcinoma (A549)	n.d.	n.d.	0.25	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.05

test microorganism	MIC ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)						positive control ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
	1	2	4	5	6	7	
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (DSM 10)	n.i.	n.i.	8.3	33.3	n.i.	66.6	0.42 ^G
<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i> (ATCC 700084)	n.i.	n.i.	66.6	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.83 ^G
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (DSM 346)	n.i.	n.i.	8.3	66.6	n.i.	n.i.	16.6 ^O
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (DSM 30008)	n.i.	n.i.	33.3	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.42 ^G
<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i> (DSM 30191)	n.i.	n.i.	16.6	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	8.30 ^N
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (DSM 1116)	n.i.	n.i.	33.3	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	8.30 ^N
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (PA14)	n.i.	n.i.	66.6	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	1.04 ^C
<i>Candida albicans</i> (DSM 1665)	n.i.	n.i.	4.2	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	1.67 ^G
<i>Mucor hiemalis</i> (DSM 2656)	n.i.	n.i.	8.3	n.i.	n.i.	66.6	8.30 ^N
<i>Rhodotorula glutinis</i> (DSM 10134)	n.i.	n.i.	4.2	33.3	n.i.	66.6	8.30 ^N
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i> (DSM 70572)	n.i.	n.i.	4.2	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	4.20 ^N
<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i> (DSM 6766)	n.i.	n.i.	16.6	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	1.70 ^K

^a(*) Slight inhibition of cell proliferation. (**) No cytotoxic activity observed. n.d., not determined; n.i., no inhibition up to 67 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$; C, ciprofloxacin; G, gentamicin; K, kanamycin; N, nystatin; and O, oxytetracycline.

Figure 9. Inhibitory activity of compounds 1–3 and 5–8 against biofilm formation of *S. aureus*. The solvent control (MeOH) was used as the baseline, and its average value was set as 0% inhibition. Microporenic acid A (MAA) was used as a positive control. Error bars indicate SD of duplicates in two biological repeats; *p* values: (***) *p* < 0.001, (**) *p* < 0.01, and (*) *p* < 0.05.

UHPLC, Thermo Scientific, Inc., Waltham, MA, U.S.A.) was employed. Analysis was performed applying the following conditions: solvent A [deionized H₂O + 0.1% formic acid (FA)], solvent B [acetonitrile (MeCN) + 0.1% FA], gradient: starting at 5% B for 0.5 min increasing to 100% B in 19.5 min then holding 100% B for 5 min, flow rate 0.6 mL min⁻¹, UV-vis detection 190–600 nm. A maXis ESI-time-of-flight (TOF) mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) was used to acquire the HR-ESI-MS data. It was equipped with an Agilent 1200 Infinity Series HPLC-UV system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, U.S.A.) using the same column and separation gradient as for the HPLC-DAD-MS analysis. Additional parameters: scan range, *m/z* 100–2500; rate, 2 Hz; capillary voltage, 4500 V; and dry temperature, 200 °C. The 1D/2D NMR spectra of the isolated compounds were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 500 MHz spectrometer equipped with BBGO (Plus) Smartprobe (¹H, 500 MHz; ¹³C, 125 MHz) and/or a Bruker Avance

III 700 MHz spectrometer utilizing a 5 mm TCI cryoprobe (¹H, 700 MHz; ¹³C, 175 MHz). Compounds were dissolved in methanol-*d*₄ (δ_{H} 3.310; δ_{C} 49.00) or chloroform-*d* (δ_{H} 7.260; δ_{C} 77.160).

Fungal Material and Identification. Two strains of *Laburnicola nematophila*, namely, 20AD (DSM 112866) and K01 (DSM 112867); DSMZ—German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany), were isolated from the infected eggs of cereal cyst nematode *Heterodera filipjevi* collected in n Yozgat, Turkey.¹³ Molecular phylogenies using combined sequence data were conducted. The acquired sequences for *L. nematophila* 20AD and K01 strains using four genome loci markers were registered on the GenBank database with respective accession numbers.¹³ The isolates were cultured on YM6.3 agar (D-glucose, 4 g L⁻¹; malt extract, 10 g L⁻¹; yeast extract, 4 g L⁻¹; agar, 20 g L⁻¹, adjusted to pH 6.3, before autoclaving) in the dark.

Cultivation and Metabolite Extraction. Seed culture of individual strains, each containing 200 mL of Q6/2 medium (D-glucose, 2.5 g L⁻¹; glycerol, 10 g L⁻¹; cottonseed flour, 5 g L⁻¹, pH 7.2) in a 500 mL Erlenmeyer flask, were inoculated with 5 × 25 mm² sections of mycelium grown on YM6.3 agar and cultivated at 23 °C with shaking at 140 rpm in the dark. After reaching sufficient biomass, the culture broth was homogenized using an Ultra-Turrax (T25 easy clean digital, IKA) equipped with an S25 N-25F dispersing tool at 10,000 rpm for 10 s. This seed culture served as the inoculum for subsequent cultivations on BRFT medium (100 mL of a solution of K₂HPO₄, 0.5 g L⁻¹; sodium tartrate, 0.5 g L⁻¹; yeast extract, 1 g L⁻¹, added to 28 g of brown rice and autoclaved) which was inoculated with 6 mL of the Q6/2 media seed culture.

Solid-State Fermentation. An initial cultivation of *L. nematophila* 20AD (DSM 112866) was performed as described above using six Erlenmeyer flasks. Two flasks were harvested after 2, 3, and 4 weeks, respectively, following incubation in the dark at room temperature. After the respective incubation periods, each flask was extracted with 3 × 250 mL of acetone, mixed thoroughly, and processed according to a previously described protocol.⁵ The resulting crude extracts were defatted by liquid-liquid partitioning between *n*-heptane and methanol. Both solvent fractions were evaporated to dryness and analyzed by HPLC-DAD-MS.

Based on these results, a scale-up cultivation of strain 20AD was conducted, with 12 flasks harvested after 4 weeks and 8 flasks after 6 weeks under the same conditions. In parallel, strain K01 (DSM 112867) was cultivated in 35 and 15 flasks, respectively, using the same parameters as described above.

Isolation of Compounds 1–8. The screening cultivation of *L. nematophila* 20AD (DSM 112866) on BRFT medium yielded 1.3 g of crude methanol extract and 2.2 g of *n*-heptane extract. A subsequent scale-up cultivation on BRFT medium produced an additional 2.2 g of methanol extract. Strain K01 was cultivated on BRFT medium affording 3.8 g of the crude methanol extract. Purification of all crude extracts was performed according to the workflow shown in Figures S62–S63 for 20AD and Figure S64 for K01 and the conditions are described Tables S2–S14, respectively. Initial fractionation was carried out using a FlashPure ID silica cartridge on a Grace Reveleris X2 flash chromatography system. The resulting fractions were further purified by reversed-phase preparative HPLC. This process yielded 1 (1.2 mg), 2 (3.1 mg), 3 (1.1 mg), 5 (1.5 mg), 7 (2.6 mg), 8 (1.2 mg) from methanol extracts and 4 (13.1 mg) from *n*-heptane extract of strain 20AD, whereas strain K01 afforded 6 (2.1 mg).

Cordypyridone E (1): Yellow amorphous solid; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +106$ (*c* 0.07, MeOH); UV/vis (MeOH): λ_{\max} ($\log \epsilon$) = 284 (4.1), 224 (4.2) nm; ECD (*c* = 8.14×10^{-4} M; MeOH): λ [nm] ($\Delta\epsilon$) 246 (+1.6), 218 (+36.1) nm; NMR data (^1H NMR: 500 MHz, ^{13}C NMR: 125 MHz, methanol-*d*₄), see Table 1; HR-(+)-ESI-MS: *m/z* 290.1749 [M - H₂O + H]⁺ (calcd. 290.1751 for C₁₇H₂₄NO₃⁺), 308.1857 [M + H]⁺ (calcd. 308.1856 for C₁₇H₂₆NO₄⁺), 330.1674 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd. 330.1676 for C₁₇H₂₅NNaO₄⁺); *t*_R = 7.56 min (LC-ESI-MS).

Cordypyridone F (2): Yellow amorphous solid; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +153$ (*c* 0.1, MeOH); UV/vis (MeOH): λ_{\max} ($\log \epsilon$) = 289 (3.8), 216 (4.4) nm; ECD (*c* = 8.14×10^{-4} M; MeOH): λ [nm] ($\Delta\epsilon$) 292 (+0.5), 270 (+0.4), 218 (+56.1) nm; NMR data (^1H NMR: 500 MHz, ^{13}C NMR: 125 MHz, methanol-*d*₄), see Table 1; HR-(+)-ESI-MS: *m/z* 308.1855 [M + H]⁺ (calcd. 308.1856 for C₁₇H₂₆NO₄⁺), 330.1672 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd. 330.1676 for C₁₇H₂₅NNaO₄⁺); *t*_R = 6.86 min (LC-ESI-MS).

Cordypyridone G (3): Yellow amorphous solid (limited purity); $[\alpha]_D^{20} -492$ (*c* 0.08, MeOH); UV/vis (MeOH): λ_{\max} ($\log \epsilon$) = 285 (3.5), 258 (3.4), 212.5 (4.2) nm; ECD (*c* = 9.03×10^{-4} M; MeOH): λ [nm] ($\Delta\epsilon$) 294 (+0.6), 266 (+0.3), 218 (+28.1) nm; NMR data (^1H NMR: 700 MHz, ^{13}C NMR: 175 MHz, methanol-*d*₄), see Table 1; HR-(+)-ESI-MS: *m/z* 278.1748 [M + H]⁺ (calcd. 278.1751 for C₁₆H₂₄NO₃⁺), *t*_R = 6.88 min (LC-ESI-MS).

Cordypyridone H (4): Yellow amorphous solid; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +106$ (*c* 0.04, MeOH); UV/vis (MeOH): λ_{\max} ($\log \epsilon$) = 290.5 (3.0), 218.5 (3.7) nm; ECD (*c* = 4.51×10^{-4} M; MeOH): λ [nm] ($\Delta\epsilon$) 263 (+0.3), 251 (-0.3), 216 (+17.3) nm; NMR data (^1H NMR: 500 MHz, ^{13}C NMR: 125 MHz, methanol-*d*₄), see Table 1; *m/z* 278.1751 [M + H]⁺ (calcd. 278.1751 for C₁₆H₂₄NO₃⁺), 300.1567 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd. 300.1570 for C₁₆H₂₃NNaO₃⁺); *t*_R = 11.26 min (LC-ESI-MS).

Cordypyridone I (5): Yellow amorphous solid; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +88$ (*c* 0.1, MeOH); UV/vis (MeOH): λ_{\max} ($\log \epsilon$) = 250.5 (3.8), 212 (4.0), 204 (4.0) nm; ECD (*c* = 14.16×10^{-4} M; MeOH): λ [nm] ($\Delta\epsilon$) 227 (-2.6), 198 (+26.0) nm; NMR data (^1H NMR: 700 MHz, ^{13}C NMR: 175 MHz, methanol-*d*₄), see Table 2; HR-(+)-ESI-MS: *m/z* 354.2061 [M + H]⁺ (calcd. 354.2064 for C₂₂H₂₈NO₃⁺), *t*_R = 10.19 min (LC-ESI-MS).

Cordypyridone J (6): Yellow amorphous solid (limited purity); $[\alpha]_D^{20} +16$ (*c* 0.1, MeOH); UV/vis (MeOH): λ_{\max} ($\log \epsilon$) = 223 (3.7), 206 (3.9) nm; ECD (*c* = 13.55×10^{-4} M; MeOH): λ [nm] ($\Delta\epsilon$) 277 (+2.8), 220 (+8.0), 198 (+12.3); NMR data (^1H NMR: 500 MHz, ^{13}C NMR: 125 MHz, methanol-*d*₄), see Table 2; HR-(+)-ESI-MS: *m/z* 370.2013 [M + H]⁺ (calcd. 370.2013 for C₂₂H₂₈NO₄⁺); *t*_R = 9.25 min (LC-ESI-MS).

Cordypyridone C (7): Yellow amorphous solid; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +176$ (*c* 0.09, MeOH); UV/vis (MeOH): λ_{\max} ($\log \epsilon$) = 292 (3.2), 217 (3.9) nm; ECD (*c* = 4.30×10^{-4} M; MeOH): λ [nm] ($\Delta\epsilon$) 256 (+0.8), 239 (+1.2), 218 (+27.5) nm (Figure S53); NMR data (^1H NMR: 500 MHz, ^{13}C NMR: 125 MHz, methanol-*d*₄) comparable to those reported in literature;¹⁴ HR-(+)-ESI-MS: *m/z* 292.1912 [M + H]⁺

(calcd. 292.1907 for C₁₇H₂₆NO₃⁺), 314.1723 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd. 314.1727 for C₁₇H₂₅NNaO₃⁺); *t*_R = 11.23 min (LC-ESI-MS).

Cordypyridone D (8): Yellow amorphous solid; $[\alpha]_D^{20} +106$ (*c* 0.07, MeOH); UV/vis (MeOH): λ_{\max} ($\log \epsilon$) = 291.5 (3.2), 217.5 (3.9) nm; ECD (*c* = 16.29×10^{-4} M; MeOH): λ [nm] ($\Delta\epsilon$) 242 (+3.4), 220 (+72.1), 211 (+42.1) nm (Figure S61); NMR data (^1H NMR: 500 MHz, ^{13}C NMR: 125 MHz, methanol-*d*₄) comparable to those reported in literature;¹⁴ HR-(+)-ESI-MS: *m/z* 290.1746 [M - H₂O + H]⁺ (calcd. 290.1751 for C₁₇H₂₄NO₃⁺), 308.1856 [M + H]⁺ (calcd. 308.1856 for C₁₇H₂₆NO₄⁺), 330.1672 [M + Na]⁺ (calcd. 330.1676 for C₁₇H₂₅NNaO₄⁺); *t*_R = 7.04 min (LC-ESI-MS).

Antimicrobial Assay. The antimicrobial activity assay was performed applying a serial dilution methodology. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the isolated metabolites were determined against a panel of Gram-positive, Gram-negative bacteria and fungi applying our previously described protocol.²³

Cytotoxicity Assay. Compounds (1, 2, and 4–7) were evaluated for their cytotoxic activity against seven different cell lines using the MTT assay [3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide], as previously described.²⁴ Epithilone B served as a positive control.

Nematicidal Assay. Nematicidal effects were assessed using *Caenorhabditis elegans* in a 48-well flat-bottom plate. Metabolites (1, 2, 4, and 6–8) were tested at the concentrations 100, 50, and 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in biological triplicates as described by Phutthacharoen et al.²⁴ Ivermectin was used as a positive control at the concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and methanol was used as a negative control. The percentage of mortality was corrected by applying the Schneider–Orelli formula, which accounts for the observed baseline mortality in the negative control.²⁵

Biofilm formation. The inhibitory activity against biofilm formation of *Staphylococcus aureus* was assessed by applying the same protocol as previously described.²⁶ Briefly, *S. aureus* DSM 1104 was revived from a -20 °C stock in 25 mL of CASO medium at 37 °C in a 250 mL flask for 20 h. The resulting culture was adjusted to an OD₆₀₀ equivalent to 0.001 McFarland standard, and 150- μL aliquots were transferred to 96-well tissue culture plates (TPP, reference number 92196, Switzerland) containing CASO medium supplemented with 4% glucose. Serial dilutions of compounds 1–3 and 6–8: ranging from 125–1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$; 5: ranging from 125 to 0.004 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were added to the wells. Plates were incubated at 37 °C with shaking at 150 rpm for 20 h. Following incubation, wells were washed and stained with crystal violet to quantify biofilm biomass. Methanol (2.5%) was used as the solvent control, and microporenic acid A (MAA; 125–1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) served as the positive control. All experiments were performed in at least two independent biological replicates, each with technical duplicates. Statistical significance was evaluated using Student's *t*-test (two-tailed, unpaired), and *p* values categorized as follows: (***) *p* < 0.001, (**) *p* < 0.01, and (*) *p* < 0.05. Error bars represent standard deviation (SD).

Computational Section. Within the realm of electronic circular dichroism (ECD) spectra elucidation, all possible conformations of compounds 1–8 were obtained by performing a conformational analysis by means of Omega2 software²⁷ (with an energy window of 10 kcal/mol).

The obtained conformations were subjected to geometrical optimization followed by frequency calculations at the B3LYP/6-31+G* level of theory. Upon frequency calculations, Gibbs free energies were calculated. Based on the optimized geometries, the time-dependent density functional theory (TDDFT) computations were performed at the CAM-B3LYP/TZVP level of theory to identify the first 50 excitation states. According to the reported literature, the employed level of theory is appropriate for TDDFT–ECD calculations.^{28,29} For each compound, the ECD spectra of the conformers were Boltzmann averaged and graphed by adopting the SpecDis 1.71 using Gaussian band shapes with a sigma value of 0.20–30 eV.^{30,31} All quantum mechanics calculations were conducted using Gaussian09 software.³² All calculations, including geometry optimization and TDDFT computations, were carried out in methanol

solvent employing the integral equation formalism variant (IEFPCM) model.^{33,34}

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jnatprod.5c00768>.

LR-ESI–MS, HR-ESI–MS, 1D (¹H/¹³C), 2D (¹H–¹H COSY, HMBC, HSQC, and ROESY) NMR, and ECD spectra of compounds 1–8 (PDF)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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pathways

Explore the platform

